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Research Article

ANALYSIS OF HEARING LOSS AND USE OF HEARING AIDS AMONG CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS IN PAKISTANDr Rao Shahzad Ahmad¹, Dr Muhammad Abu Bakar², Dr Seerat Fatima³¹Medical Officer at DHQ Hospital, Rajanpur²Medical Officer at BHU Golay Wali, Khushab³Mohi ud Din Islamic Medical College, Mirpur**Abstract:**

Introduction: Current data suggest that approximately 5% of the world's population 32 million adults and 34 million children and adolescents suffer from disabling hearing loss, defined as hearing loss greater than 40 dB hearing levels (dB HL) in the better hearing ear in adults and greater than 30 dB HL in the better hearing ear in children. **Objectives of the study:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the hearing loss and use of hearing aids among children and adolescents in Pakistan. **Methodology of study:** This cross sectional study was conducted at DHQ Hospital, Rajanpur during January 2019 to September 2019. The data was collected from 100 hearing and speech impaired children. We select these participants to find the oral health status of these children. All children of 5-15 years of either gender having speech & hearing impairment were included in the study. The clinical examination was carried according to World Health Organization (WHO) techniques. **Results:** The data were collected from 200 children. Out of these children, bleeding on probing was found in 72 (13.3%) female children as compared to 57 (10.6%) male children. While 131 (24.3%) female children had calculus, 124 (23.0%) male children had the same condition. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that high prevalence of dental caries was observed among hearing and speech impaired children. There is a high need for an epidemiological survey followed by the comprehensive dental care programs for children with hearing speech impairment, as well as efforts should be taken to encourage and promote parents of these children to improve their oral health.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hearing loss is the fourth highest cause of disability globally. Current data suggest that approximately 5% of the world's population 32 million adults and 34 million children and adolescents suffer from disabling hearing loss, defined as hearing loss greater than 40 dB hearing levels (dB HL) in the better hearing ear in adults and greater than 30 dB HL in the better hearing ear in children [1]. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) adverse impacts of unaddressed (untreated) disabling hearing loss, cause annual global costs of over 660 billion Euros [2].

These overall costs include expenses associated with the health-care and education systems (direct costs), costs including productivity losses due to absenteeism from work as well as income loss by family members caring for a disabled child (indirect costs) and costs for accessibility, adaptation and social inclusion for people with disabilities (intangible/societal costs) [3].

In the 21st century, communication disorders (which include hearing impairment, HI) constitute a serious concern within public health; if not treated, there are negative effects on the economic well-being of a society in the era of communication. The problem deserves to be highlighted, as the sense of hearing is essential for the development of speech, language and learning, and the higher the degree of hearing impairment, the greater the difficulties in perceiving and distinguishing speech, including language deficits [4].

In children under the age of 15, 60% of hearing loss occur due to avoidable causes, and estimates indicate that 1.1 billion people around the world could be at risk for hearing impairment due to unsafe hearing practices, such as the use of individual audio devices [5]. Adolescents deserve close attention, as they are exposed to high levels of non-occupational noise. Some factors associated with hearing impairment include infections of the superior air

passages and middle ear, in addition to the presence of cerumen obstructing the external acoustic meatus, as these can interfere in the transmission of the hearing stimulus. However, despite the fact that the causes of HI can be identified in children and adolescents, data are limited regarding possible risk factors for acquired HI [6].

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyse the hearing loss and use of hearing aids among children and adolescents in Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF STUDY:

This cross sectional study was conducted at DHQ Hospital, Rajanpur during January 2019 to September 2019. The data was collected from 100 hearing and speech impaired children. We select these participants to find the oral health status of these children. All children of 5-15 years of either gender having speech & hearing impairment were included in the study. The clinical examination was carried according to World Health Organization (WHO) techniques. The children were then examined for oral status by making them sit on the upright chair in adequate light using autoclaved instruments; plain mouth mirror and WHO probe. Caps, gloves, masks and gauze were used in accordance with infection control guidelines.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was carried out using the SPSS Version 17. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for all the qualitative variables. Mean & SD were calculated for all the quantitative variables.

RESULTS:

The data were collected from 200 children. Out of these children, bleeding on probing was found in 72 (13.3%) female children as compared to 57 (10.6%) male children. While 131 (24.3%) female children had calculus, 124 (23.0%) male children had the same condition.

Table 01: Distribution of periodontal status according to the gender among hearing impaired children

	Periodontal status (CPI)			χ^2	P
	Healthy 0, n (%)	Bleeding 1, n (%)	Calculus 2, n (%)		
Gender					
Male	81 (15.0)	57 (10.6)	124 (23.0)	1.695	0.429 (NS)
Female	75 (13.9)	72 (13.3)	131 (24.3)		
Total	156 (28.9)	129 (23.9)	255 (47.2)		

P<0.05. *n*=Number of children; NS=Not significant; CPI=Community periodontal index

87% of the children required single surface or double surface restorations, the remaining were indicated for pulp therapy. Gingivitis was seen in 35% of the children with bleeding gums and calculus who required oral prophylaxis. The study showed that 19% of the subjects had malocclusion which constituted anterior open bite seen in 3%, crowding in 11% and class II malocclusion seen in 3%. Fractured anterior teeth were seen among 3.9% of the children examined.

Table 02: Gender-wise distribution of dental caries

Gender	Caries free		Caries present		Total
	n	%	n	%	
Male	29	66	18	56	47
Female	15	34	14	44	29
Total	44	100	32	100	76

DISCUSSION:

Dental treatment is the greatest unmet health need of the handicapped child. This statement by Nowak was substantiated by various studies done globally on special children. Similarly, in the present study, the overall dental caries prevalence of the sample was 65% with a drastic portion of the sample (91.7%) needing one or the other treatment [7]. This distressing condition can be ascribed to communication barriers faced by these children in various parts of the world. Recently, another study done by Wei *et al.* on 229 senior high school deaf students comparing 196 healthy adolescence reported a caries prevalence rate of 55.9%. Many other studies done solely on CHI reported wide variations in caries prevalence rates [8]. Suma reported a prevalence rate of 42% with decayed component of the index being the highest. Al-Qahtani and Wyne reported a prevalence of 91% and 95% in 6-7 and 11-12-year-old CHI, respectively. Shyama *et al.* reported a prevalence rate of 84.6% with 86% of the caries lesions still untreated [9]. Rao *et al.* reported a prevalence rate of 65.1%. Meaningful comparison of caries prevalence rates cannot be made from these studies as there are wide variations in age distribution of the sample selected in each study; however, all these studies signify the devastating situation of CHI concerning oral health [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that high prevalence of dental caries was observed among hearing and speech impaired children. There is a high need for an epidemiological survey followed by the comprehensive dental care programs for children with hearing speech impairment, as well as efforts should be taken to encourage and promote parents of these children to improve their oral health.

REFERENCES:

1. Franks AS, Winter GB. Management of the handicapped and chronic sick patient in dental practice. *Br Dent J.* 1974 Feb;136(3):107–110.
2. Bear PN., Benjamin SD. Periodontal disease in children and adolescents. Philadelphia, USA: JB Lippincott Company; 1974. pp. 255–270.
3. Jain M, Mathur A, Kumar S, Dagli RJ, Duraiswamy P, Kulkarni S. Dentition status and treatment needs among children with impaired hearing attending a special school for the deaf and mute in Udaipur, India. *J Oral Sc.* 2008 Jun;50(2):161–165.
4. Oredugba FA. Oral health care knowledge and practises of a group of deaf adolescents in Lagos, Nigeria. *J Public Health Dent.* 2004;64(2):118–120.
5. Ubido J, Huntington J, Warburton D. Inequalities in access to health care faced by women who are deaf. *Health Soc Care Community.* 2002 Jul;10(4):247–253.
6. Nunn JH. The dental health of mentally and physically handicapped children: A review of the literature. *Community Dent Health.* 1987 Jun;4(2):157–168.
7. Nagaraja Rao G. Oral health status of certified school children of Mysore state: A report. *J Indian Dent Assoc.* 1985 Feb;57(2):61–64.
8. Simon EN, Matee MI, Scheutz F. Oral health status of handicapped primary school pupils in Dares Salaam, Tanzania. *East Afr Med J* 2008;85:113-7.
9. Al-Qahtani Z, Wyne AH. Caries experience and oral hygiene status of blind, deaf and mentally retarded female children in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Odontostomatol Trop* 2004;27:37-40
10. Wei H, Wang YL, Cong XN, Tang WQ, Wei PM. Survey and analysis of dental caries in students at a deaf-mute high school. *Res Dev Disabil* 2012;33:1279-86.